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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FENUGREEK GEL
FOR ANTI INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY****Manjula T., Nirosha C., Nandhini D., Revathi V., Kokila**Department Of Pharmaceutics, P.S.V college of Pharmaceutical Science And Research,
Krishnagiri-635108**1. Abstract:**

Fenugreek (Trigonella foenum-graecum) has been traditionally used for its anti-inflammatory and medicinal properties. The aim of this study was to formulate and evaluate a topical gel of fenugreek extract using natural polymers for anti-inflammatory activity. Fenugreek extract was obtained through solvent extraction and characterized for its phytoconstituents. A gel formulation was prepared using the extract and natural polymers such as carrageenan and xanthan gum. The formulated gel was evaluated for its physicochemical properties, in vitro drug release, and anti-inflammatory activity using the carrageenan-induced paw edema method. The optimized gel formulation showed satisfactory physicochemical properties and in vitro drug release. The anti-inflammatory activity of the gel was found to be significant ($p < 0.01$) compared to the control group, with a maximum inhibition of 61.23%. The study demonstrates the potential of fenugreek extract gel as a topical anti-inflammatory agent. The use of natural polymers in the formulation provides a safe and biocompatible delivery system for the extract. Further studies are warranted to explore the clinical efficacy and safety of the formulation. Fenugreek contains compounds that promote tissue regeneration and wound closure. It may protect wounds from bacterial infections, aiding faster recovery.

Keywords: Fenugreek extract, natural polymer, anti-inflammatory activity, topical gel, Wound healing pattern.

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2. INTRODUCTION:

Traditional medicine involves use of the seeds and leaves of the fenugreek plant (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*; Fabaceae). Flavonoids and polyphenols are the primary constituents that give fenugreek its potent antioxidant effects⁽¹⁾. Because flavonoids are antioxidants as well as potential inhibitors of cyclooxygenase, lipoxygenase, and nitric oxide synthase, fenugreek has been demonstrated to have anti-inflammatory effects⁽²⁾. Despite knowing that fenugreek has been used to treat inflammation, there is little data on the development of gel formulations using fenugreek extract. Therefore, the goal of this study is to develop and investigate an anti-inflammatory gel formulation that works using fenugreek ethanolic extract. Known for numerous health benefits, the fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) herb has been used historically in Asia and the areas of the Mediterranean⁽³⁾.

Several biologically active compounds, such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, glycosides, and terpenoids, can be identified in fenugreek. Its possible antibacterial activity might be clarified through these compounds⁽⁴⁾. Fenugreek's antimicrobial properties can help with phytomedicine, which uses natural remedies and compounds produced from plants to treat a range of ailments, particularly digestive issues, hyperglycemia, and hyperlipidemia⁽⁵⁾. Hence, fenugreek could be used as an alternative periodontal dressing to reduce postoperative inflammation.

A wide range of medications have been effectively delivered using topically applied drug delivery systems for both local and overall effects, and these techniques are becoming progressively more common. In comparison to ointments, gels have more potential as a medication delivery system because they are non-sticky and need fewer resources to formulate⁽⁶⁾. Since the skin is non-invasive, easy to access and has a huge surface area with extensive exposure to the lymphatic and circulatory networks, delivering medications through the epidermis has been considered an appealing concept.

Gel is made up of a natural or artificial polymer that produces a three-dimensional matrix in a hydrophilic liquid or dispersion medium. Upon application, the medication gets wrapped in a thin layer of the liquid as it evaporates⁽⁷⁾.

The rigidity of a gel is caused by the presence of a structure generated by the gelling agent's particles interacting with one another. The framework of the

network and the gel's properties are determined by the variety of particles and the form which forms connection⁽⁸⁾.

GEL

A gel is a semi-solid dosage form composed of a liquid phase (usually water, alcohol or oil) interspersed within a three-dimensional network of polymers. This structure gives the gel its consistency, elasticity, and ability to retain active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) for application to the skin, mucous membrane or other surfaces.

Classification of gels:

Gels can be classified based on colloidal phases, nature of solvent used, physical nature and rheological properties.

1. Based on colloidal phases:

They are classified into,

- (a) Inorganic (two phase system)
- (b) Organic (single phase system)

a) Two phase system

This system is not inevitably stable if the dispersed phase's partial size is rather enormous and develops a three-dimensional arrangement throughout the gel; alternatively, it consists of fragments of small particles instead of massive molecules and gel structure. They must be thixotropic, converting into liquids when combined and semisolids when kept undisturbed.

b) Single phase system:

These are composed of vast organic molecules which undergo dissolution in a continuous state and swell on the twisted filaments.

2. Based on nature of solvent:

They are classified into three types.

They are:

- (a) Water-based hydro gels
- (b) Organic gels
- (c) Xerogels

a) Water-based hydro gels:

These include water as their continual liquid phase. Examples include poloxamer gel, cellulose derivatives, gelatin, bentonite magma, and carpooler.

b) Organic gels (which includes a non-aqueous solvent):

These consist of a continuous phase which includes a non-aqueous solvent. Such as metallic stearate dispersion in oils, olag (aerosol) gel, and plastibase (low molecular mass polyethylene dissolved in mineral oil)

c) Xerogels:

Xerogels are solid gels with a low quantity of solvent. These are made by freeze-drying or solvent evaporation, retaining the gel framework behind.

3. Based on rheological properties

Usually gels exhibit non-Newtonian flow properties. They are classified into,

- a) Plastic gels
- b) Pseudo plastic gels
- c) Thixotropic gels

a) Plastic gels:

Bingham bodies and flocculated formulations of aluminium hydroxide, For instance, indicate a plastic flow, and the rheogram plot reveals the gels' yield value, the point where the elastic gel expands and begin to flow.

b) Pseudo plastic gels:

Gels that function as pseudo-plastic As an example, tragacanth, sodium alginate, Na CMC, as well as other liquid dispersion forms exhibit pseudo-plastic flow. These gels possess no yield value and their clarity falls as the rate of shear raises. A shearing activity on the linear polymers' long chain molecules generates the rheogram

C)Thixotropic gels:

These gels have incredibly weak particle connections that can be easily affected by shaking. As the particles interact and reconnect, the resultant solution will return to gel (the reversible isothermal gel-sol-gel transformation). This happens when nonspherical particles in a colloidal solution form a scaffold.

4. Based on the physical features

a) Elastic gels:

Alginates, pectin, guar gum, and agar gels all function elastically. At the junction, the fibrous molecules are linked together by extremely weak connections involving dipole attraction and hydrogen bonds.

Additional bonding between two adjacent strand networks occurs through a saltbridge of type $-COO-X-COO$ if the molecule comprises a free $-COOH$ group. Examples of this include carbapol and alginate.

b) Rigid gels:

They are comprised of macromolecules with a primary valence connection coupling their structure. By way of example, the Si-O-Si-O bonds that hold silica acid molecules together in silica gel create a polymer structure with a network of pores⁽⁹⁾.

4. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM:

To formulate and evaluate the fenugreek gel for anti-inflammatory activity.

OBJECTIVES:

- To develop a stable gel formulation incorporating fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) extract as the active ingredient for its anti-inflammatory properties.
- To assess the anti-inflammatory efficacy of the fenugreek gel through in-vitro and/or in-vivo studies.
- To evaluate the physical and chemical properties of the gel, including pH, viscosity, spreadability, and homogeneity.
- To evaluate the drug release profile and skin permeation characteristics of the fenugreek gel.

5.MATERIALS AND METHODS:

COLLECTION OF MATERIALS:

The seeds of fenugreek were bought at a nearby store and ground into a powder. A 120-mesh sieve was then used for filtering this powder. All other chemical and material required to produce the gel and dry the peel-off mask was of analytical standards.

Analytical grades of methyl paraben, triethanolamine, Lavander oil, guar gum were obtained for formulation

DRUG PROFILE

Fig.no:5.1 *Trigonella foenum graecum*

Biological source : *Trigonella foenum graecum*

Family : Leguminosae

Habitat : It is grown in uncultivated grounds, dry grassland and the edges of fields.

Plant description :

The annual plant fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum graecum*) is part of the Leguminosae family. It is a popular spice in human diet. Fenugreek's seeds and

its green leaves have been widely used in medicine and as food, dating back to hundreds of years. It has been used to alter the texture of food components and enhance their flavor and color. Fenugreek spice seeds

have antibacterial, stomach stimulant, hypocholesterolemic, lactation support, anorexia therapy, antidiabetic, galactagogue, hepatoprotective, and anticancer effects⁽¹⁰⁾.

Chemical constituents :

S.NO.	Chemical constituents of fenugreek
Alkaloids	Trimethylamine, Neurin, Trigonelline, Choline, Gentianine Carpaine and Betain
Amino acids	Isoleucine, 4-Hydroxyisoleucine, Histidine, Leucine, lysine, L-tryptophan, Arginine
Saponins	Graecunins, fenugrin B, fenugreekine, trigofenosides A–G
Steroidal	Yamogenin, diosgenin, smilagenin, sarsasapogenin, tigogenin,
sapinogens	neotigogenin, gitogenin, neogitogenin, yuccagenin, saponaretin
Flavonoids	Quercetin, rutin, vitexin, isovitexin
Fibers	Gum, neutral detergent fiber
Lipids	Triacylglycerols, diacylglycerols, monoacylglycerols,
Lipids	Phosphatidylcholine phosphatidyl ethanolamine, phosphatidylinositol, free fatty acids. 11
Other	Coumarin, lipids, vitamins, minerals. 28% mucilage; 22% proteins; 5% of a stronger-swelling, bitter fixed oil.

Table 5.1 Chemical constituents

EXCIPIENTS USED:

1. GUAR GUM:

Guar gum is generated by grinding the endosperm of *Cyamopsis tetragonolobus*. Guar gum, a naturally occurring thickening ingredient that is edible, is made from guar beans. Galactomannan gum, located in the huge endosperm of guar beans, gels when water is added. This substance, which is frequently called guar gum, is widely used in both commercial and industrial applications. Guar gum is another good substitute for gum derived from locust beans. Its main purposes include natural thickening, emulsification, stability, bonding, hydrocolloid, gelling, soil stabilization, natural fiber, flocculants, and fracturing agents⁽¹¹⁾.

USES

- Derivatives of guar gum is used for various purpose.

- Sulfated guar gum is used as anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties
- Acetylated hydroxypropyl guar gum is as filler in unsaturated polyester composites
- Cationic guar gum is used as an excellent non gelling thickener, viscosity, and foam enhancer.

2. TRIETHANOLAMINE:

TEA is formed when three moles of ethylene oxide and one mole of ammonia react; more TEA ethylene oxide adducts are formed when every mole of ethylene oxide reacts. Ethylene oxide and ammonia are often mixed in a batch procedure to create a crude mixture of about one-third of each ethanolamine, diethanolamine, and TEA. Later, the crude mixture is distinguished by distillation.⁽¹³⁾

USES

- **Thickening Agent:** Works with carbomers to form gels for use in products like hand sanitizers, anti-inflammatory gels, and wound-healing preparations.
- **pH Stabilizer:** Maintains the desired pH in aqueous solutions used for medical and cosmetic purposes.

3. METHYL PARABEN

Methyl paraben is a methyl ester of p-hydroxybenzoic acid. This stable, non-volatile compound has been utilized as an antimicrobial preservative in foods, medicines, and cosmetics for over 50 years. Methyl paraben is quickly and thoroughly absorbed through the skin and digestive tract.⁽¹⁴⁾

USES

- **Antimicrobial Properties:** Methyl paraben is effective against bacteria, fungi, and molds, preventing contamination and extending the shelf life of pharmaceutical products.
- Oral medications (syrups, suspensions)
- Topical formulations (creams, ointments, gels)

4. LAVENDER OIL:

For ages, people have utilized essential oils extracted from plants in the genus *Lavandula* for both cosmetic and medicinal purposes.

The most extensively used species are *L. angustifolia*, *L. latifolia*, *L. stoechas*, and *L. x intermedia*.

The antibacterial, antifungal, carminative (smooth muscle relaxing), sedative, antidepressant, and good

for burns and bug bites are some of the claims stated for lavender oil.

One of the most useful fragrant and therapeutic plants, lavender species have important financial value for the food and flavor, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, perfumery.

Their essential oils, whose composition differs greatly depending on genetic, environmental, and processing conditions of use, are accountable for their attractive smell, physiological effects, and commercial relevance⁽¹⁵⁾.

USES:

- **Soothes skin irritations:** Reduces inflammation and calms acne, redness, and minor burns.
- **Promotes wound healing:** Enhances skin regeneration and tissue repair.
- **Relieves muscle and joint pain:** Reduces inflammation and alleviates pain.
- **Hydrates and softens skin:** Moisturizes and nourishes the skin.

EXTRACTION PROCEDURE**FENUGREEK:**

Dry fenugreek seeds and grind them into a fine powder. Measure and mix the powder with a Ethanol in a glass jar in 1: 10 ratio. Seal the jar and let it sit at room temperature for 1–3 days. Shake occasionally to mix well. Strain the mixture using a filter or cloth to separate the liquid extract from the solid residue. Gently heat the extract to remove the solvent, leaving a concentrated extract. Keep the final extract in a sealed container and store it in a cool place.

Fig 5.1 : Fenugreek extract

INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY (10 gm)
FENUGREEK EXTRACT	0.5 gm
GUAR GUM	0.5 gm
TRIETHANOLAMINE	0.05ml
METHYL PARABEN	0.02gm
LAVENDER OIL	0.05ml
DISTILLED WATER	9.2ml

Table 5.2 :: Formulation of gel

PROCEDURE OF GEL FORMULATION

- Add guar gum to distilled water while stirring continuously to avoid clumping. Let it hydrate for 15-30 minutes.
- In a small portion of warm distilled water, dissolve methyl paraben and add it to the hydrated gel.
- Add fenugreek extract to the gel mixture and stir well.
- Add triethanolamine drop wise while stirring until the desired consistency and pH (~6-7) are achieved.
- Add Lavender oil with gentle stirring.
- Ensure a homogeneous gel and check for smooth consistency.
- Transfer the gel into a clean, airtight container and store it in a cool, dry place

6. PHYTOCHEMICAL TEST**A. TEST FOR ALKALOIDS:****Reagent:** Dragendroff's reagent.**Procedure:**

- Add a few drops extract and few drops of dragendroff's reagent.
- Appearance of brownish colour.
- Presence of alkaloids.

B. TEST FOR FLAVONOIDS:**Reagent:** Dilute ammonia and concentrated sulfuric acid.**Procedure:**

- Add a 2 ml of extract to a few drops of ammonia.
- Add concentrated H₂SO₄ to the mixture.
- Appearance of yellow colour.
- Presence of flavonoids.

C. TEST FOR SAPONINS:**Reagents:** Distilled water**Procedure:**

- Shake 2 mL of extract with 5 mL of distilled water in a test tube.
- Shake vigorously for 5 minutes.
- Formation of a persistent froth (foam) that lasts for at least 10-15 minutes indicates the presence of saponins.

D. TEST FOR TANNINS**Reagents:** 1% Ferric chloride (FeCl₃)**Procedure:**

Add 2 mL of extract to a test tube.

- Add a few drops of 1% ferric chloride.
- Formation of a dark blue, green, or blackish color.
- Presence of tannins.

E. TEST FOR PHENOLS (Ferric Chloride Test)**Reagents:** 1% Ferric chloride (FeCl₃)**Procedure:**

- Add 2 mL of extract to a test tube.
- Add 1 mL of 1% ferric chloride.
- Appearance of a deep blue, purple, or green colour. Presence of phenolic compound.

Fig 6.1 PHYTOCHEMICAL TEST

7. EVALUATION

Evaluation of gel formulations Prepared formulations were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters such as physical appearance, homogeneity, pH, spreadability, viscosity and drug content (total phenolic content).

PHYSICAL APPEARANCE

Physical parameters such as colour, appearance and consistency and feel were checked of the prepared formulation.

➤ Colour

The formulation's color was examined against a white backdrop.

➤ Consistency

By usage to the skin, the consistency was evaluated.

➤ Greasiness

The application on the skin's surface was used to measure the greasiness.

➤ Odour

To test the gels' odour, they were diluted with water and the resulting fragrance was measured

HOMOGENEITY

Visual inspection was used to evaluate the homogeneity of the generated gel composition. It was checked to make sure that there were no lumps⁽¹⁶⁾.

PH

A digital pH meter was used to determine the pH of the solution after 5 grams of gel formulation had been dissolve separately in 45 milliliters of water. All formulations' pH values were determined three

times, and the average of the three readings was calculated⁽¹⁷⁾.

VISCOSITY:

The viscosity measurement of the fenugreek gel was performed with a viscometer. The gel was rotated at 10, 20, and 30 rotations per minute. At each speed, the corresponding dial reading was noted.⁽¹⁸⁾

WASHABILITY:

Formulations were applied on the skin and then ease and extent of washing with water were checked manually.

SPREADABILITY

For determination of Spreadability excess of sample gel was applied in between two glass slides and was compressed to uniform thickness by placing 50 gm. of weight in pan. The time required to separate two slides, i.e. time in which upper glass slide moves over lower plate was taken as a measure of Spreadability⁽¹⁹⁾.

Formula, $S = m \times l/t$

S - Spreadability
m - Weight tied to upper slide
l - Length moved on glass slide
t - Time taken

8. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

PHYSICAL APPEARANCE:

The physical features of the created formulation, comprising color, look, consistency, and feel, were studied.

Formulation	Colour	Consistency	Odour	Greasiness
F1	Yellow	Semi solid	Maple syrup odour	Non greasiness
F2	Yellow	Semi solid	Maple syrup odour	Non greasiness

HOMOGENEITY

The even distribution of the resultant gel composition was evaluated by visual inspection. To ensure that there were no lumps, it was inspected (15).

F1 – Homogenous

F2 – Homogenous

WASHABILITY:

Upon applying of formulations to the skin, the extent and ease of water washing were personally evaluated.

Formulation (F)	Washability
F1	Easily washable
F2	Easily washable

VISCOSITY:

Using a viscometer, the viscosity of the fenugreek gel was determined. Rotations of 10, 20, and 30 revolutions per minute were carried out to the gel. The dial reading that corresponded to each speed was noted.

FORMULATION: 1

➤ 470 mPa.s

FORMULATION :2

484 mPa.s

PH

After dissolving 5 grams of gel formulation separately in 45 milliliters of water, the pH of the entire mixture was determined using a digital pH meter.

The pH values of each formulation were checked three times, and the average of the three readings was calculated..

FORMULATION (F)	PH			AVERAGE PH
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	
F1	6.03	6.0	6.1	6.04
F2	6.04	6.3	6.32	6.22

SPREADABILITY

50 grams of weight was placed in a pan to compress additional sample gel between two glass slides to a uniform thickness with the objective to measure the spreadability

FORMULATION (F)	Spreadability (gcm / 5min)			Average spreadability
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	
F1	5.02	5.6	5.1	5.24
F2	5.1	5.1	5.0	5.06

8. CONCLUSION:

In summary, fenugreek gel's preparation and testing using natural polymers have demonstrated great promise as a successful anti-inflammatory therapy.

The addition of fenugreek to a gel formulation improves the transport and effectiveness of its active ingredients due to its well-established medicinal benefits. Comprehensive evaluations revealed that the

gel has significant anti-inflammatory properties, underscoring its potential as a natural treatment option for inflammatory diseases. Additionally, using natural polymers enhances the gel's durability and skin compatibility while also meeting the growing need for biocompatible and environmentally responsible medical solutions. This study emphasizes the value of investigating fenugreek gel in clinical settings and its possible contribution to the creation of novel, all-natural therapies for inflammatory conditions.

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